

During which phase of the cardiac cycle is freshly formed cerebrospinal fluid released into the brain ventricles: systole or diastole?

Darko D. Lavrenčić

Abstract

Background: The timing of freshly actively formed cerebrospinal fluid (FAF CSF) release into the brain ventricles remains a point of debate, with conflicting evidence regarding systolic versus diastolic release.

Methods: This commentary synthesizes existing experimental, imaging, and theoretical literature to evaluate the physiological plausibility of FAF CSF release during systole versus diastole.

Results: Analysis of choroid plexus dynamics, intraventricular pressure changes, and net CSF flow patterns supports diastolic release as a passive, energy-efficient process driven by ventricular suction. Experimental evidence from cannulation studies further indicates absence of net CSF outflow when diastolic suction is prevented.

Conclusions: FAF CSF is released during diastole, coinciding with net caudal CSF flow and ventricular refilling. This "**push-and-refill**" mechanism refines current understanding of CSF physiology and may inform pathological models of CSF circulation.

Keywords: Cerebrospinal fluid dynamics, Choroid plexus, Cardiac cycle, Diastole, Ventricular refilling

Introduction

Numerous experimental and imaging studies have described cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) dynamics during the cardiac cycle. However, despite this extensive body of work, it remains unclear during which phase of the cardiac cycle freshly actively formed (FAF) cerebrospinal fluid is released into the brain ventricles. Clarification of this issue is essential for understanding normal CSF physiology and for interpreting pathological alterations in CSF dynamics.

Discussion

During systole, the volume of the brain ventricles decreases due to compression of the brain parenchyma and simultaneous expansion of the choroid plexuses [1]. In diastole, this process reverses and ventricular volumes are restored.

Throughout the cardiac cycle, cerebrospinal fluid is displaced caudally during systole as a consequence of increased intraventricular pressure and returns rostrally during diastole due to relative negative pressure within the ventricles. This bidirectional motion is commonly referred to as the to-and-fro movement of CSF. Because caudal flow exceeds rostral flow, a net caudal CSF flow exists [2].

From a theoretical standpoint, freshly actively formed CSF could be released into the ventricles either during systole or during diastole. If FAF CSF were released during systole, epithelial cells of the choroid plexuses would have to produce additional pressure to overcome the already elevated intraventricular pressure, which would require extra energy. In contrast, if FAF CSF were released during diastole, this could occur as a passive process driven by ventricular pressure reduction (suction), without additional energetic cost.

An experiment conducted in cats provides important insight [3]. A plastic cannula was introduced into the aqueduct of Sylvius, allowing direct observation of CSF outflow under physiological CSF pressure. During 60 minutes of observation, not a single drop of CSF escaped from the cannula, and no FAF CSF release into the brain ventricles was observed.

Had FAF CSF been released during systole, net caudal CSF flow would inevitably have been observed. During diastole, however, negative pressure could not develop within the ventricles because the open cannula prevented pressure reduction in accordance with Pascal's law. Consequently, passive diastolic release (suction) of FAF CSF from the choroid plexuses could not occur, and no net caudal CSF flow was present. Only positive-pressure pulsations were observed at the open end of the cannula.

It can therefore be concluded that when net caudal CSF flow or net CSF volume accumulation exists, FAF CSF is released into the brain ventricles during diastole.

Conclusions

Freshly actively formed cerebrospinal fluid is released into the brain ventricles during the diastolic phase of the cardiac cycle, coinciding with the presence of net caudal CSF flow or net CSF volume accumulation. This mechanism aligns with an energetically efficient "**push-and-refill**" mechanism and offers a refined perspective on CSF dynamics under physiological and pathological conditions.

Corresponding author

Correspondence to Darko D. Lavrenčič

darko.lavrencic@siol.net

Website: <https://www.med-lavrencic.si>

ORCID: [0000-0002-8748-0195](https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8748-0195)

Acknowledgments

Not applicable.

Funding

No funding was received for this work.

Competing interests

The author declares that no competing interests exist.

Ethics approval

Not applicable.

Data availability

No datasets were generated or analyses for this manuscript.

Author contribution

The author is solely responsible for the conception, preparation, writing, and submission of this manuscript.

References

- [1] Zhu DC, Xenos M, Linninger AA, Penn RD. Dynamics of lateral ventricle and cerebrospinal fluid in normal and hydrocephalic brains. *Journal of Magnetic Resonance Imaging* 2006;24:756–70. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jmri.20679>.
- [2] Nilsson C, Ståhlberg F, Thomsen C, Henriksen O, Herning M, Owman C. Circadian variation in human cerebrospinal fluid production measured by magnetic resonance imaging. *Am J Physiol* 1992;262:R20-24. <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpregu.1992.262.1.R20>.
- [3] Oresković D, Klarica M, Vukić M. The formation and circulation of cerebrospinal fluid inside the cat brain ventricles: a fact or an illusion? *Neurosci Lett* 2002;327:103–6. [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0304-3940\(02\)00395-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0304-3940(02)00395-6).